

in this case both the current efficiency and the throwing power are so low that the cathode surface is not completely covered with the alloy coating even after 90 minutes of electrolysis.

The chromium-molybdenum alloy is best obtained when the SO_4/CrO_3 ratio in the plating solution is 1/100, which is also the optimum value for chromium plating (Table IV). At the lower concentration of sulphuric acid, an oxide coating containing both chromium and molybdenum is formed. A bright coating containing 0.8% of molybdenum was produced when the SO_4/CrO_3 ratio was 1/50, but in this case the cathode was only partly coated owing to the poor throwing power of the solution.

The author is much indebted to Professor C. G. Fink, Head of the Division of Electrochemistry, Columbia University, U.S.A., since deceased, for suggesting the problem. The experimental part of the investigation was carried out in the Electrochemical Laboratory of the Columbia University.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE, CALCUTTA.

Received October 29, 1956.

[Jour. Indian Chem. Soc., Vol. 34, No. 5, 1957]

ELECTROLYTIC ZINC POWDER

By S. C. SHOME

Spongy zinc has been prepared by the electrolysis of sodium zincate solution at room temperature; the sponge crumbles to a fine powder when washed with water and dried. Brass is found to be the suitable cathode and zinc, the anode. Zinc sponge is best obtained from a solution containing 20 to 30% NaOH and 3 to 6% zinc at a cathodic C.D. of 20 to 35 amp./dm². The average current efficiency of zinc deposition is 78%.

In obtaining one pound of zinc powder by the electrolysis of sodium zincate solution using a rotating zinc anode, half immersed in the electrolyte, 0.7 Kw/hr. of electrical energy is required. If an insoluble anode, such as nickel, is employed, 1.5 Kw/hr. of energy is consumed per pound of zinc powder produced.

Zinc powder finds extensive use as a reducing agent in various chemical processes. It is an essential material for the manufacture of sodium hydrosulphite and Rongalite C, which are largely employed in the reduction of dyestuffs in textile industries. Zinc powder is also required for the production of zinc alloys in powder metallurgy.

The methods which can be employed for the preparation of zinc powder are as follows: (i) as a byproduct in the pyrometallurgy of zinc, (ii) by the application of a jet of air to atomize a column of molten zinc, and (iii) by the electrolysis of zinc salt solutions. The powder obtained by method (iii) is chemically more active than that obtained by any of the other methods.

Morgan and Ralston (*Chem. Met. Eng.*, 1916, 15, 465) studied the formation of zinc sponge from zinc sulphate, zinc chloride or sodium zincate solution by the electrolytic method; the sponge obtained by electrodeposition crumbled to a fine powder when dried. Sebborn (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1933, 29, 825) studied the formation of zinc sponge by the electrolysis of zinc sulphate solution and was of the opinion that the formation of zinc sponge was linked up with the production of zinc hydroxide at the cathode. He found that the spongy deposit of zinc from sulphate solution was favoured by low concentration of metal ion and by the use of high current densities. Sebborn (*ibid.*, 1933, 29, 659) further showed that the zinc powder was spontaneously oxidised to zinc oxide with evolution of heat, when the powder was coated with a thin film of alkali and exposed to air. He considered that sodium and potassium hydroxides dissolved the surface film of the oxide from the metallic zinc, forming sodium zincate and potassium zincate respectively. The combined effect of the heat of this reaction and the removal of the protective oxide film from the zinc powder caused further oxidation of the zinc powder.

Morgan and Ralston (*loc. cit.*) electrolysed sodium zincate solution at 4.5 volts, employing a stationary zinc anode and an iron cathode. In the present investigation zinc has been deposited from sodium zincate solution at 1.4 volts using a slowly rotating zinc anode. This device saves more than 50% of electrical energy consumed per pound of zinc powder. At this low voltage oxygen does not evolve at the anode during electrolysis and, hence, the concentration of zinc ion in the solution remains unchanged. Further, it is observed that brass is a better cathode material than iron, since the hydrogen over-voltage on brass has a higher value than on iron. The other optimum conditions for the production of zinc powder by the electrolysis of sodium zincate solution have also been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

The sodium zincate solution was prepared by dissolving freshly precipitated zinc hydroxide in sodium hydroxide solution and was electrolysed in a glass beaker at room temperature. The average current efficiency of zinc deposition was 78%. The electrolytic zinc powder contained 93 to 94% zinc.

The various conditions under which spongy zinc has been deposited from zincate solution are summarised in Table I. The electrolysis of sodium zincate solution, employing an insoluble anode, produced oxygen at the anode and the concentration of zinc ion in the solution gradually decreased (Expt. 1, Table I). Similar evolution of oxygen was observed at high current densities even when zinc was the anode material. There was, however, no oxygen evolution during the electrolysis of zincate solution when the C. D. at the zinc anode was low. But after one hour, the voltage of the cell gradually increased from 1.2 to 4.0 and oxygen evolution commenced at the anode (Expt. 3). The rise in voltage and the oxygen evolution at the zinc anode could be prevented by any of the following methods: (a) decreasing the anode current density, (b) slowly stirring the liquid near the anode surface, (c) slowly rotating the anode when it was circular, and

(d) removing the black film from the anode surface from time to time. The circular zinc anode was half immersed in the electrolyte and was slowly rotated to and fro manually during electrolysis. The use of Ni as an insoluble anode resulted in the decrease of zinc ion concentration in the solution. The attempt to replenish zinc slowly by keeping an asbestos bag containing zinc hydroxide in suspension in the anolyte was not satisfactory.

Zinc was also deposited in spongy form by the electrolysis of zinc sulphate solution (2 to 3% $ZnSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$) using zinc anode and aluminium cathode. This method was found unsuitable for practical purpose, since the electrical resistance of dilute zinc sulphate solution was high and the current efficiency of zinc deposition from such a solution was low.

TABLE I
Electrodeposition of zinc from zincate solution.
Temperature of solution = 25° to 28°.

Expt. No.	Conc. of NaOH (g./100 c.c.)	Zn content of soln. (g./100 c.c.)	Cathode.	Anode.	C.D. (amp./dm ²) at		Voltage of cell.	Remarks.
					Cathode.	Anode.		
1	20	4.0	Brass	Nickel	35	16	3.2	Oxygen evolved at anode and Zn^{2+} conc. in soln. gradually decreased.
2	30	6.6	"	Zinc (stationary)	30	16	4.5	Same as in Expt. 1.
3	20	4.0	"	"	20	6	1.2	No oxygen evolution at anode and Zn^{2+} conc. in soln. did not change for one hour.
4	20	4.0	"	Zinc disc* (rotating)	20	16	1.4	No oxygen evolution at anode and Zn^{2+} conc. in soln. remained unaltered.
5	20	3.5	"	Nickel [enclosed in asbestos bag containing $Zn(OH)_2$ suspended in zincate soln.]	20	16	4.5	Oxygen evolved at anode. Half the zinc deposited came from $Zn(OH)_2$ dissolved in anode chamber.

* Half immersed in the electrolyte.

The electrolytic zinc powder, when washed thoroughly with water to make it free from alkali, could be dried without any difficulty. For determining zinc content, the sodium zincate solution was acidified with 6N- H_2SO_4 and titrated with $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ using diphenylamine as internal indicator. The purity of the zinc powder was estimated by the ferric alum method as developed by Edwards (*Chem. Met. Eng.*, 1919, 21, 192).

DISCUSSION

Reactions at the Cathode.—During the electrolysis of sodium zincate solution, the reactions occurring at the cathode are:

The formation of hydrogen molecules by the discharge of hydrogen ions is a highly polarised reaction (eq. 2), and even at high current densities mostly zinc is deposited on the cathode (eq. 1). The hydrogen overvoltage on brass has a higher value than the same on iron; brass is therefore found to be a better cathode material than iron for electrodeposition of zinc.

Zinc is deposited in powdery form as the zincate solution is electrolysed. At the commencement of electrodeposition zinc nuclei are formed at the cathode surface and then grow to small particles as the electrolysis continues. The sodium zincate solution also contains colloidal particles of zinc hydroxide, which are negatively charged. At high current densities zinc hydroxide is deposited in a thin layer around the growing zinc particles and puts a stop to their further growth. This happens when the concentration of colloidal zinc hydroxide at the cathode surface increases in proportion to zinc ion concentration. New zinc nuclei are then formed and the process is repeated. Zinc is thus obtained at the cathode in the form of fine powder coated with a thin layer of hydroxide.

Reactions at the Anode.—The anodic reactions are :

When an insoluble anode, such as nickel, is used (Expt. 1), oxygen is evolved by the discharge of OH^- ions (eq. 4). With a zinc anode, the soluble zincate ions are formed (eq. 3) and the anodic product removes itself continuously from the anode surface. At a sufficiently high C.D., the liquid next to the anode surface becomes saturated with sodium zincate, and then other anodic processes, such as discharge of OH^- ions requiring a higher electric energy consumption, become possible. As OH^- ions are discharged, first of all an oxide film is formed, followed by the evolution of oxygen. The presence of an oxide film on the zinc surface will hinder further production of zincate ions by the dissolution of the zinc anode. This anodic passivity may be avoided if the liquid near the anode surface is slowly stirred so that fresh alkali can attack the zinc surface. This stirring can be conveniently effected by employing a slowly rotating circular anode, half immersed in the electrolyte (Expt. 4).

With a stationary anode, the insoluble film formed on its surface at high current densities is loose and can easily be removed by scratching with a glass rod. Once this film is removed, the anodic polarisation is reduced and electrolysis proceeds again at a low voltage without any evolution of oxygen. This is in accord with Evans' theory ("Metallic Corrosion, Passivity and Protection", Arnold, 1946, p. 15) which attributes passivity of metals to the formation of insoluble films on their surfaces.

The author wishes to express his sincere thanks to Dr. J. C. Ghosh for his interest in the work and encouragement. The experimental part of this investigation was carried out at the Chemical Laboratories of the Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore.